

Support to the Activities of the
Concentrated Solar Thermal
Technology Area of the SET Plan

September 23-26, 2025
Almeria, Spain
31st SolarPACES Conference

SIDE EVENT: EU CST PROJECTS & RESEARCH AGENDA

Date and time	25 th September, 2025
Time	9:00 – 11:00 CEST
Hybrid event	Physical next to SolarPACES Conference and online
Registration	Free registration for online participants here

This event is organized in the framework of the CST4ALL project, and focuses on EU-funded research in Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST) and how these projects contribute to fulfilling the CST Implementation Plan of the SET-Plan.

The workshop will feature several EU-supported CST projects, which will present their objectives, main results, and perspectives on future developments. It will conclude with a round-table discussion on EU funding and future research requirements to meet the goals of the CST Implementation Plan.

Agenda

9:00	Introduction & EU-funded CST projects overview Daniel Benitez, DLR
9:10	MSA-Trough project Diogo Canavarro, University of Evora
9:25	ASTERIx-CAESar project Fritz Zaversky, Cener
9:40	Sun-to-Liquid II project José González-Aguilar, IMDEA Energy
9:55	SolarSCO2OL & SHARP-sCO2 projects Rafael Guedez, KTH
10:10	SALTOPower project Radia Ait El Cadi, University of Evora
10:25	HySelect project Kai Risthaus, DLR
10:40	Round-Table: Current CST funding frameworks, discussion on future funding requirements.
11:00	End of the workshop

CST4ALL team reserves the right to make changes to the workshop program

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101075408.

CST4ALL Coordinator

Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

Projects contributing to this event

MSA-Trough (GA 101122276) Development of a parabolic Trough concentrator system for Molten Salt Application ([link](#))

ASTERIx-CAESar (GA 101122231) Air-Based Solar Thermal Electricity For Efficient Renewable Energy Integration & Compressed Air Energy Storage ([link](#))

Sun-to-Liquid II (GA 654408) Integrated solar-thermochemical synthesis of liquid hydrocarbon fuels ([link](#))

SolarSC020L (GA 952953) SOLAR based sCO2 Operating Low-cost plants ([link](#))

SHARP-sCO2 (GA 101083899) Solar Hybrid Air-sCO2 Power Plants ([link](#))

SALTOPower (GA 101079303) European facility on Molten SALT technologies TO power and energy system applications ([link](#))

HySelect (GA 101101498) Efficient water splitting via a flexible solar-powered Hybrid thermochemical-Sulphur dioxide depolarized Electrolysis Cycle ([link](#))

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